

Towards a more responsible assessment

Savonia University of Applied Sciences'

CoARA Action Plan 2026-2029

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Approved by Savonia's extended management team on 13.5.2026

1 Introduction

Savonia University of Applied Sciences is committed to the [CoARA agreement](#), which renews the evaluation of researchers and research, with the aim of making evaluation practices more responsible.

At a university of applied sciences, applied research and the natural movement of staff between education and research are commonplace. To obtain a comprehensive picture of multidimensional activities and their impact, it makes sense to carry out a comprehensive assessment based on qualitative indicators of research activities and expert work. The objectives of the CoARA agreement provide a useful framework for the development of Savonia University of Applied Sciences' research activities and the development of personnel competence assessment and career path models. Broadly, the CoARA commitment supports our efforts to describe the responsibility and impact of our operations.

The CoARA agreement and belonging to the CoARA community provide an opportunity to develop fair and transparent evaluation of research and researchers together with other higher education institutions, both nationally and internationally. As a member of the European Network of Higher Education Institutions, we also consider international co-creation important for the mobility of our experts.

The Universities of Applied Sciences Act lays down a regional development task for universities of applied sciences, which is carried out through RDI activities. Due to the nature of RDI activities, the experts of Savonia University of Applied Sciences have always had a wide-ranging impact on regional development work and carried out applied research

together with regional actors, such as companies and communities.

Savonia University of Applied Sciences does not engage in the inappropriate use of journal and publication-based indicators. At universities of applied sciences, the importance of scientific publishing has always been moderate, because we publish new information primarily for the professional public.

2 Responsible Assessment of Research

Person responsible: Vice Rector Mikko Vuoristo

Objective

We base the evaluation of research primarily on qualitative evaluation, in which peer review plays a central role and is supported by the responsible use of quantitative indicators.

Benefits

We will obtain an even broader picture of the impact of Savonia's RDI activities regionally and more broadly. We can direct our activities even better to benefit actors in the region.

Current state

Currently, the evaluation is based on monthly, semi-annual and annual reporting.

Qualitative and quantitative assessments of research fields are carried out in connection with the financial statements and interim reports. Quantitative indicators currently include the amount of project funding, the number of international projects, the implementation rate, the actual costs and the amount of RDI business on a monthly basis.

In addition to these, the development of the project base by field of research and the cross-use of human resources are measured every six months. The number of publications is measured annually.

Qualitative indicators are used to examine the integration of research fields with education, continuous learning and other fields of research, the quality of partnership activities, the diversity of funding sources and feedback received from partners.

Individual projects are evaluated in the project steering groups and in a separate evaluation carried out before the end of the project. Currently, Savonia's projects and their results are evaluated approximately six months before completion. The evaluation is qualitative and focuses on the usability, effectiveness and identification of reuse opportunities for the results achieved in the project. For individual projects, qualitative feedback is also collected in the project steering groups.

Measures to achieve the goal

1. Development of systematic qualitative peer review of research fields and research themes

Systematic qualitative peer review of research fields and research themes is developed in cooperation with other Finnish universities of applied sciences in the RDI management network.

Peer review will be developed through pilots in cooperation with partners. The aim is to establish a procedure for evaluating of research activities in universities of applied sciences in accordance with the SCOPE model. After the pilot phase, the evaluation will be expanded, where applicable, to include the assessment of research themes.

Responsibilities

Principal responsible: Vice Rector Mikko Vuoristo

Other persons in charge: Head of the research field to be appointed at a later date and representation of the research staff

Resourcing

The piloting phase will be carried out within the framework of the normal resources of the research field. The aim is to build a cost-effective model. In addition to the staff of the research fields, the Vice Rector will participate in the piloting of the evaluation of research fields.

Schedule

Pilot projects will be conducted in 2026. The continuation will then be planned with the selected partners over the next few years.

2. Development of project evaluation

The content of the project evaluation will be expanded by identifying and introducing indicators describing qualitative impact. The project evaluation is based on Savonia's values and considers impact objectives such as environmental impacts, social impacts, regional interaction, technological impact, impact on regional business activities and the development of education. The knowledge base collected on stakeholder cooperation will be expanded and its usability will be improved. The SCOPE model is utilised in the development of project evaluation.

The extension of the project evaluation will be tested through a pilot. Lessons learned from the pilot will be used to expand the approach to all RDI projects, taking into account differences in project scale.

Responsibilities

Principal responsible: Vice Rector Mikko Vuoristo

Other responsible persons: RDI manager and his or her team to be appointed later for the project evaluation pilot, other persons involved in the development of the project evaluation

Resourcing

The development of the project evaluation will be carried out within the framework of normal resources. The aim is to build a cost-effective assessment model.

Schedule

The development of the project evaluation has begun and the piloting will be carried out during 2026.

3 Responsible Assessment of Researcher

Person responsible: HR Director Minna Kaija-Kortelainen

At the heart of the CoARA commitment is the idea that the merits of researchers should be examined more comprehensively. CoARA expands the assessment to consider, for example, different professional skills and the societal impact of research.

Definition of a researcher

The assessment of the researcher could also be referred to as assessment of experts. The job title as such is not significant for the responsible assessment, but the content of the work is decisive.

"Researchers are defined as persons who participate in various ways in professional activities aimed at producing new knowledge, applying knowledge in a new way, or developing and utilising it in teaching."

[Draft of the FIN-CAM assessment tool 2025, Responsible Science.](#)

At Savonia University of Applied Sciences, the CoARA commitment will be expanded to cover all personnel, and for a more comprehensive picture, the personnel will be described as an expert in the future.

Objective

We recognise the competence and merit of experts extensively and support their professional development in their work with the help of career path models. The career path model is transparent and impartial.

We will develop and implement a responsible assessment model in Savonia that is suitable for universities of applied sciences. We raise awareness of responsible assessment and the processes in which it is used. It is important that competence management and responsible assessment practices are clear to everyone and ensure equal, non-discriminatory and equal treatment.

Benefits

With the help of the responsible assessment model, we can better identify the expertise of experts and utilise it more flexibly. We can also develop the competence of the entire

organisation. A transparent career path model and an equal remuneration process increase experts' trust in the employer and strengthen Savonia's goal of being the most responsibly influential higher education institution.

Current state

The development of career path models has been started by establishing phenomenon-based fixed-term principal lecturer roles. Phenomenon-based principal lecturers have been assessed using a transparent assessment model, which is further developed with the help of the CoARA implementation plan.

Savonia does not currently use any other systematic responsible assessment of experts. Savonia's current recruitment and evaluation practices are described in both the non-discrimination and equality plan, as well as in the work community development plan, personnel programme and instructions for supervisors. Recruitment already makes use of a versatile assessment, which can include an interview as well as various assessments, such as teaching demonstrations, assignments or external assessment. The evaluation is carried out by the recruitment selection group, and the Rector of Savonia makes the final selection decisions.

Recruitment

In recruitment, attention is paid to ensuring that recruitment is open, transparent and merit-based and supports diverse career paths. The selection emphasises competence, equality and diversity that are essential to the position and the organisation. Applicants will be provided with clear information about the position, selection criteria and career prospects. Supervisors participating in the recruitment process are ensured orientation on the principles of fair recruitment at Savonia.

Diversity is promoted in recruitment by ensuring that recruitment and selection procedures are transparent, equitable and competence based. Applicants are evaluated based on their requirements and merits, without discrimination or unfavourable treatment, for example, due to their career path, background or personal characteristics. Recruitment practices support the formation of equal and diverse teams and the development of a fair and inclusive operating culture.

Recruitment practices have been documented and will be updated if necessary.

The requirements of the Non-Discrimination Act and the Equality Act are considered in recruitment. The Equality Act (section 6) imposes an obligation on employers to act in such a way that both women and men apply for vacant positions. The responsibility of the recruitment process is manifested in the definition of the position and the selection criteria (how the selection criteria do not limit the group of applicants), the call for applications (using as many different application channels as possible) and the evaluation of applicants (e.g. by taking into account the differences between applicants in the interview situation), selection for the interview and the actual interview phase.

Recruitment considers the applicants' entire career and values diverse skills, especially those acquired in working life. In the selection panel, the assessment is based on diverse expertise and appropriate representation from different fields of Savonia (e.g. education and RDI). Various selection methods are already used in recruitment (e.g. interviews, assignments, videos, demonstrations and external evaluation), but the range of methods must be further diversified, considering the principles of responsible evaluation of experts.

Career advancement and career paths

The Employment Contracts Act (Employment Contracts Act, Chapter 2, Section 1) obliges employers to strive to promote the employee's opportunities to develop at work according to their abilities to advance in their careers. Above all, an employee's opportunities to develop in their work, increase their skills and advance in their careers are affected by well-functioning processes and practices. It is also important to pay attention to the solutions made in everyday life that are part of career advancement: who is hired for new projects, who is assigned more challenging tasks or who is sent to training.

The various opportunities for development offered by employers at work must be made possible for everyone equally, promoting non-discrimination and equality. According to the Employment Contracts Act, the employer must both treat everyone equally and strive to promote the employee's opportunities to develop and advance in their careers according to their abilities. Other personal qualities must not be an obstacle to career advancement.

Measures to achieve the goals

1. Development of a model that supports the responsible assessment of experts

For systematic and transparent assessment, a responsible assessment tool suitable for human resources management will be used. Among other things, the suitability of the FIN-CAM tool will be tested. The FIN-CAM tool is being tested in the RDI team.

2. Reforming recruitment to align with responsible assessment of researcher

Recruitment forms are being developed to support responsible evaluation. A CV based on TENK's model will be introduced and systematically utilised in recruitment.

In recruitment, a wide range of expertise and research related to expert and research work are identified. Recruitment evaluation practices will be used to better identify and document scientific and societal merits, transparent and participatory research, the diverse activities of an expert or researcher (e.g. teaching and pedagogy, strong professional skills, supervision and mentoring, societal engagement and impact), and diverse roles in working life and different communities.

Supervisors are trained in the responsible evaluation of experts in recruitment.

3. Reforming career models from the perspective of responsible assessment

For expert and support staff (note: the definition of a personnel group in accordance with the applicable collective agreement), a career path model for researchers will be introduced (Junior Researcher, Researcher, Principal Investigator)

Regarding teaching staff, the assessment criteria will include elements of responsible assessment. A permanent assessment framework will be created to help teachers assess responsibly, with the key criteria affecting merit. Teachers assess their own achievements, for example, in connection with a development discussion.

Responsibilities

Principal responsible: HR Director Minna Kaija-Kortelainen

Other responsible persons: Working group (Mikko Ylilauri, Riitta Turjamaa, Suvi Aura, Minna Kaija-Kortelainen, Tiina Kuiri), Pilot teams from the working group members' teams (Fin-CAM, recruitment), HR specialist

Resourcing

The development work and piloting will be carried out within existing development resources

Schedule

Career path model work begins in spring 2026.

TENK's CV for recruitment, where applicable, will be piloted in the recruitment of RDI personnel in autumn 2026.

Testing of the Fin-CAM tool among RDI personnel starts in autumn 2027

4 Promotion and communication of the CoARA action plan

Persons responsible: Anne Heikkinen, Director of Communications, Mira Juppi, Head of Information Services (until 12.6)

Objective

The content and measures of the CoARA implementation plan are well understood by personnel. Orientation on the responsible evaluation of researchers and research will be organised for those involved as the implementation plan progresses. The CoARA implementation plan is progressing according to the agreed schedule.

Benefits

The development of the responsible assessment of researchers and research is a wide-ranging change in operations. With open and timely communication, the change becomes a shared priority for the entire staff. Comprehensive and accessible communication increases understanding and trust in the transparent evaluation of personnel and research and in

Savonia University of Applied Sciences' efforts to promote high-quality and fair and equal operations.

Measures

The CoARA commitment and the CoARA action plan will be published on Savonia's website and on Savonia's intranet. The CoARA action plan will be archived in Zenodo in accordance with the terms of the CoARA commitment.

A website will be created for CoARA on Savonia's intranet, where materials explaining the background of the CoARA commitment and the CoARA implementation plan will be presented in an understandable way. The progress of the measures will be actively communicated in the news on Savonia's intranet, and the news will be archived on the CoARA website.

Savonia's employees know who is responsible for promoting CoARA measures and can contact the responsible persons without barriers.

Information sessions and training on the responsible evaluation of experts at Savonia will be organised for the personnel. Training on responsible evaluation of research is organised for those participating in the evaluation of projects and research fields.

Ongoing measures

The progress of the CoARA implementation plan is regularly presented to Savonia's extended management team and communicated to all Savonia personnel on the intranet.

Evaluation procedures affecting personnel are discussed in Savonia's cooperation working group.

Savonia has a representative in the national CoARA branch. Those responsible participate in the national CoARA development in their own national reference groups.

Resourcing

The measures will be embedded as part of Savonia's normal communications and training activities.

Schedule

Continuous throughout the action plan period.

Appendix 1. Timeline for CoARA measures